

SOCIAL SCIENCES

SUSTAINABLE FINANCING DEVELOPMENT AND CHALLENGES IN GEORGIA

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"In today's world, working on sustainable financing issues is no longer an option, it is now a necessity"

Abstract

The Sustainable Finance Roadmap for Georgia summarizes all possible actions that the NBG intends to implement regarding the sustainable finance development over the next three to four years. The ultimate goal of this roadmap is to create a credible, predictable and stable regulatory framework and prepare the market for transitioning to sustainable finance. It aims to support the incorporation of sustainability issues into decision-making by providing coherent and consistent actions and allowing time for the system to adapt. The Roadmap is structured around six pillars, divided into Core and Supporting Pillars. The Core Pillars include several key areas like embedding ESG considerations (including climate and nature-related issues) into risk-assessment frameworks and decision-making processes of financial institutions; supporting transparency and accurate reporting that would eventually guide more capital flows towards sustainable activities; and embedding sustainability principles into the internal operations and workflows of the National Bank of Georgia. The Supporting Pillars cover areas such as increasing awareness and capacity building on sustainable finance; and, strengthening collaboration with local and international partners to ensure policy alignment and knowledge sharing.

Keywords: Sustainable finance, green economics, global finance trends

Sustainable financing plays an important role in achieving the sustainable development goals, which are relevant all over the world. Georgia, as part of the world, is one of the components of this process. Access to sustainable finance for small and medium-sized companies that create a green economy and serve sustainable development goals is particularly noteworthy.

Today, we can safely say that sustainable development issues, such as environmental and social problems, are one of the most important challenges facing the world. Although these topics are increasingly discussed year after year and there are numerous initiatives aimed at creating a more stable, inclusive, and healthy environment, risks related to sustainability remain relevant. Unfortunately, the pandemic has exacerbated existing problems, especially social issues such as inequality, unemployment, access to healthcare, and more. That is why the challenges of sustainable development are more important today than ever before, especially for developing countries like us.

Everyone agrees that the sustainable development challenges facing the world require an immediate response. The financial system has a special role in this process.

Although there is no unambiguous definition of sustainable financing, we can say that it combines two main aspects: opportunities and risks. In other words, sustainable financing, on the one hand, means directing finance towards greener, sustainable and inclusive projects; On the other hand, considering environmental, social and governance (ESG) factors in investment decisions and reducing risks in this way. The National Bank's Sustainable Financing Framework is formed

around these two key issues and aims to strengthen the role of the financial system in the sustainable development of the country.

The sustainable development challenges we face require immediate responses so that public policy can adapt to the new reality. All these requires the implementation of such reforms that will contribute to the mobilization of financial resources for green, stable and inclusive economic growth. The financial system plays an important role in this process, as sustainable development cannot exist without sustainable financing - whether public or private. However, directing private capital towards more sustainable investments requires a change in the working format of the financial system. This is a necessary condition for achieving more sustainable economic growth, ensuring the stability of the financial system and promoting transparency and long-term vision in the economy. In order to ensure financial stability and promote sustainable development, it is important to consider environmental, social and other sustainable development issues in the policies of the central banks. The National Bank of Georgia, as the central bank of the country, promotes the strengthening of the role of the financial sector in the sustainable development of the country and develops a sustainable financing framework for this purpose.

Sustainable financing plays a crucial role in achieving the goals of the European Green Deal, which aims to accelerate the green transformation. This means transitioning to a green economy using sustainable technologies, industry and transport.

More specifically, what does sustainable finance mean and what is the importance of its implementation

for Georgia? Considering the critical role of the financial sector in promoting sustainable development, the National Bank of Georgia actively promotes the development of the mentioned sector in the country.

According to the World Economic Forum, despite recent increases in global demand and supply for sustainable finance, the need for financing of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) has increased, primarily in countries that are lagging far behind in implementing the Agenda 2030.

Striving for sustainability has widened global financial inequality. According to the World Economic Forum, in 2022, high-income countries (HICs) controlled 97% of newly established sustainable investment funds and also had 80% of global assets under management. On the positive side, the rise of innovative financial instruments related to sustainability, such as sustainable bonds and debt conversions, may attract investors to some developing countries.

In the complex landscape of sustainable finance and its connection to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), a significant challenge arises – the lack of information on environmental, social and governance (ESG) issues in developing countries. This is a significant barrier to integrating sustainable practices and implementing global development goals.

Dealing with these challenges requires a strategic approach. Integrated national financing frameworks and strategies related to the Sustainable Development Goals are critical to navigating this complex landscape. These frameworks can be presented in the form of guiding principles that help address various financing needs through the use of available resources. This ultimately promotes a more harmonized and practical approach to sustainable development.

The National Bank of Georgia continues to work on developing a sustainable financing framework.

Based on the achievements of the first roadmap (2019–2024), which established a solid foundation for sustainable finance in Georgia, the second roadmap (2025–2028) focuses on further strengthening the regulatory framework by updating, improving and enhancing existing regulations, guidelines and tools. It also emphasizes monitoring the implementation of regulations by the financial sector, assessing compliance, identifying gaps, and providing feedback for continuous improvement.

The aforementioned strategic document, accompanied by a corresponding action plan, aims to promote the integration of environmental, social and governance (ESG) issues in the financial sector, improve the management of financial risks related to climate change and other ESG factors, and promote Georgia's transition to a low-carbon and sustainable economy.

The second Sustainable Finance Roadmap for Georgia was developed in consultation with local and

international stakeholders, including the German Sparkasse (DSIK), the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development (EBRD), the International Finance Corporation (IFC), and the Sustainable Banking and Finance Network (SBFN), supported by IFC.

The second roadmap combines all possible measures planned by the National Bank of Georgia to develop sustainable finance in Georgia. The roadmap includes six directions, which in turn are divided into main and supporting directions. The Roadmap is structured around six pillars, divided into Core and Supporting Pillars. The Core Pillars include several key areas like embedding ESG considerations (including climate and nature-related issues) into risk-assessment frameworks and decision-making processes of financial institutions; supporting transparency and accurate reporting that would eventually guide more capital flows towards sustainable activities; and embedding sustainability principles into the internal operations and workflows of the National Bank of Georgia. The Supporting Pillars cover areas such as increasing awareness and capacity building on sustainable finance; and, strengthening collaboration with local and international partners to ensure policy alignment and knowledge sharing“.

The roadmap will be periodically reviewed and updated to reflect market conditions, emerging risks, and global trends in sustainable finance.

Finally, the path to aligning finance and investment with sustainable development goals requires enhanced public and private partnerships. As noted above, governments play a crucial role in promoting sustainable investments and implementing relevant strategies for more sustainable development by actively supporting integration.

Through incorporating sustainability principles into financial decision-making, stakeholders can work towards creating a more inclusive, sustainable, and green global economy, in accordance with the goals which is defined by the United Nations as Sustainable Development Goals.

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